

Syntheses, characterization and bioactivities of new copper(II) complexes of *N'*-[(1*E*)-1*H*-pyrrol-2-ylmethylidene]pyridine-3-carbohydrazone[†]

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Abstract : Four copper(II) complexes viz. [Cu(PPC)₂](ClO₄)₂ (1), [Cu(PPC)(bipy)](ClO₄)₂ (2), [Cu(PPC)(phen)](ClO₄)₂ (3) and [Cu(PPC)(PMDT)](ClO₄)₂ (4) have been synthesized and characterized by various physico-chemical techniques, where PPC = *N'*-[(1*E*)-1*H*-pyrrol-2-ylmethylidene]pyridine-3-carbohydrazone, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine, phen = 1,10-phenanthroline and PMDT = *N,N,N',N'',N''*-pentamethylethylenediamine. The spectra of complexes exhibit the usual line spectra for mononuclear copper(II) complexes with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.3$. Bioactivities (superoxide dismutase, antibacterial and DNA cleavage) of these complexes have also been discussed.

Keywords : Schiff base, EPR, antibacterial activity, DNA cleavage.

Introduction

The Schiff bases are playing very important role in biological systems^{1,2}. It has been noticed that copper(II) complexes as anti-inflammatory drugs are often more active than the parent ligands themselves³. Schiff bases^{4,5} are useful ligands because of their synthetic accessibility, diversities and structural varieties. During recent years coordination compounds of biologically active ligands⁶ have received much attention. A number of Schiff base complexes^{7,8} have been found potential antibacterial⁹, antifungal¹⁰ and anticancer¹¹ activities. Chelation causes drastic changes in the biological properties of the ligands and also the metal moiety. The Schiff bases are widely studied because of increasing recognition of their role in biological system^{12,13}.

As an extension of our previous work¹⁴⁻¹⁶, we now report new mixed ligand copper(II) complexes of *N'*-[(1*E*)-1*H*-pyrrol-2-ylmethylidene]pyridine-3-carbohydrazide (PPC). Biological activities of the complexes have also been investigated and discussed.

Results and discussion

All the complexes were prepared by the interaction of copper(II) salt with hydrazone Schiff base ligand (PPC)

by conventional solution method and polycrystalline product was collected. The protocol used for the syntheses of Schiff base and their copper(II) complexes are shown in Schemes 1 and 2. The Schiff base and prepared complexes were characterized by elemental analysis, FAB⁺ mass and EPR spectroscopy.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of Schiff base ligand.

Structure of the ligand :

Analytical data indicate that the condensation of nico-

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of copper(II) complexes.

tinic acid hydrazide with pyrrol-2-carboxaldehyde occurred in 1 : 1 ratio to form a heterocyclic Schiff base ligand *N*-[(1*E*)-1*H*-pyrrol-2-ylmethylidene]pyridine-3-carbohydrazone (PPC) (Scheme 1), which has been characterized by physico-chemical techniques.

UV-Visible spectra :

Copper(II) complexes of PPC show *d-d* band 598, 602, 700 and 707 nm respectively for (1), (2), (3) and (4). Electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in 100% DMSO. The first absorption band ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) *d-d* band

in all the four complexes is in the range 620–680 nm and assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, whereas second band at 380 ± 5 nm is attributed to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transition which is assigned to ligand to metal charge transfer absorption¹⁷.

IR spectra :

The tentative assignment of the significant IR spectra of the complexes (1-4) are presented in Table 1. The C=N band of the Schiff base is found to be shifted to lower

Table 1. IR frequencies of copper(II) PPC complexes

Complex	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	$\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{O})$
L ¹	1638	1534	1030	3227	-	-
1	1647	1559	1055	3271	574	440
2	1644	1570	1048	3270	546	448
3	1623	1568	1090	3272	543	446
4	1627	1588	1091	3276	560	416

energies in the spectra of all complexes, indicating the coordination via the azomethine nitrogen. This is confirmed by the bands in the range 440–464 cm^{-1} , which have been assigned to the Cu–N band¹⁸. The increase in frequency of this band in the spectra of all complexes is due to the increase band strength, again confirming the coordination via the azomethine nitrogen. In all the complexes a strong band is observed in the region 266–280 cm^{-1} , which is consistent with the Cu–N of pyridine ring as suggestive by Clark and Williams¹⁹. The presence of a strong, sharp band at ~ 1650 cm^{-1} that can be attributed to a C=O vibration. This is probably due to the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group²⁰. However some new bands

with medium to weak intensities appear in the region 395–405 cm^{-1} in the complexes under study, which are tentatively assigned to (M–O)/(M–N) modes²¹.

Electron paramagnetic resonance spectra :

The X-band EPR spectra of the copper(II) complexes of PPC (1-4) were recorded in the solid state at room temperature and also in DMSO at liquid nitrogen temperature using TCNE free radical as the 'g marker'. Representative EPR spectra of the complexes are given in Fig. 2 and EPR parameters are given in Table 2.

The g_{\parallel} for these complexes are in the range 2.212 to 2.247 and g_{\perp} are in the range 2.055 to 2.063. Kivelson and Nieman²² have pointed out that compounds having $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.3$ are ionic in nature while those with $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp} < 2.3$ are covalent in character. The g_{\parallel} values for (1-4) reveal appearance covalency with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ as the ground state. These complexes show similar features with $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. It is interesting that the relationship $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} < 2.3$ is typical of axially symmetric d^9 copper ($S_{\text{Cu}} = 1/2$) having one unpaired electron in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital²³. Similar observations were made by earlier workers²⁴ for mixed ligand copper(II) complexes. The g_{\parallel} values of the complexes are found to be $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ which indicate considerable covalent character of the M–L bond²². In complexes (1-4), all EPR signals are shifted slightly towards higher magnetic field and therefore leading to smaller g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values. This finding is in line with increased ligand field operating through $g = 2.0023 + n\xi[E_0 - E_n]$ ²⁵. The geometric parameter G , which is measure of the exchange of inter-

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of copper(II) PPC complexes ($0.003 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^{-3}$) in DMSO.

Fig. 2. EPR spectra of polycrystalline sample of 3 at RT and in DMSO (0.003 mol⁻¹ dm⁻³) at LNT.

Table 2. EPR and UV spectral parameters of the copper(II) complexes

Parameter		1	2	3	4
Polycrystalline state (298 K)	g_1	2.065	-	2.115	2.164
	g_2	2.046	-	2.049	2.043
	g_3	-	-	-	-
	g_{iso}	-	2.068	-	-
DMSO (77 K)	$g_{ }$	2.247	2.212	2.220	
	g_{\perp}	2.063	2.056	2.055	
	$A_{ }$ (G)	175	200	180	
	G	4.031	3.905	4.130	
	α^2	0.762	0.789	0.745	
	β^2	1.027	0.851	0.918	
	γ^2	1.022	0.862	0.903	
	$K_{ }$	0.773	0.672	0.684	
	K_{\perp}	0.770	0.680	0.673	
	λ_{max} (nm)		598	700	707

action between the copper centers in a polycrystalline solid has been calculated. According to Hathaway²⁶ if $G > 4$ the exchange interaction is negligible and if $G < 4$, indicates exchange interaction. The value of G for present complexes are 4.031, 3.905 and 4.130 for respectively (2), (3) and (4) indicating exchange interaction in solid state. From the low temperature EPR spectra, various bonding

parameters such as in-plane σ -bonding, in-plane π -bonding as well as out-of-plane π -bonding was evaluated by using the following expression²⁷.

$$\alpha^2 = (A_{||}/0.036) + (g_{||} - 2.0023) + 3/7(g_{\perp} - 2.0023) + 0.04$$

The orbital reduction factors $K_{||}^2$ and K_{\perp}^2 were estimated from the expression²⁸.

$$K_{||}^2 = (g_{||} - 2.0023) E_{d-d}/8\lambda_0$$

$$K_{\perp}^2 = (g_{\perp} - 2.0023) E_{d-d}/2\lambda_0$$

where $K_{||} = \alpha^2 \beta^2$, $K_{\perp} = \alpha^2 \gamma^2$ and λ_0 represents the one electron spin-orbit coupling constant for the free ion, equal to -828 cm^{-1} . Significant information about the nature of bonding in the copper(II) complexes can be derived from the magnitude of $K_{||}$ and K_{\perp} . In case of pure σ -bonding $K_{||} \approx K_{\perp} \approx 0.77$ whereas $K_{||} < K_{\perp}$ implies considerable in-plane bonding, while for out-of-plane bonding, $K_{||} > K_{\perp}$. In all the present copper(II) complexes, it is observed that $K_{||} < K_{\perp}$ which indicates the presence of significant in-plane bonding. The evaluated values of α^2 , β^2 and γ^2 of the complexes are consistent with both strong in-plane σ and in-plane π bonding. The computed value of α^2 and β^2 (Table 2) are compared with other copper(II) complexes which are ionic in nature²⁹. Therefore, present complexes may be regarded as ionic complexes.

Superoxide dismutase activity :

The superoxide dismutase activity copper(II) complexes were studied by NBT assay method^{30,31} and the catalytic activity towards the dismutation of superoxide anion was measured. Superoxide was enzymatically supplied from alkaline DMSO. The chromophore concentration value required to yield 50% inhibition of the reduction of NBT (IC₅₀) of the present complexes is graphically presented in Fig. 3. Both complexes have distorted square pyramidal geometry. The distortion of these complexes may fa-

copper(II) complexes were performed against *E. coli*, *Citrobacter* and *Viberio* sp. of bacteria as the test organism by disc diffusion method. Antibacterial assessments of the complexes were tested as a function of concentration and compared with those of standards (Chloramphenicol). Since DMSO was used as solvent, it also screened against all organisms and no activity was found. Antibacterial data are given in Table 3 and graphically presented in Fig. 4. All complexes showed lesser activity than the standard antibiotics. At 100 µg concentration the inhibi-

Fig. 3. SOD activity of copper(II) complexes of PPC, 1-4.

vor the geometrical change, which is essential for the catalysis. The IC₅₀ value observed 43, 48, 55 and 57 µM, respectively for (1), (2), (3) and (4). The difference in IC₅₀ values for the two complexes should be ascribed to the evident discrepancy between their structures. The SOD activities of the two complexes may be attributed to the flexible nature of ligand, which is able to accommodate the geometrical change from Cu^{II} to Cu^I³².

Antibacterial activity :

The *in vitro* antibacterial screening effect of the two

tion was very low compared to higher concentration and observed that complex (4) is more active than other. Difference in antibacterial activity could be depends on nature of ligands. This would suggest that chelation facilitate the activity of a complex to cross a cell membrane and can be explained by Tweedy's chelation theory³³. Similar antibacterial activity was measured by our school previously^{34,35}.

DNA cleavage activity :

The ability of the complexes is affecting DNA cleav-

Table 3. Antibacterial activity data of copper(II) PPC complexes

	Inhibition zone in mm																Standard				
	750 µg/ml				500 µg/ml				250 µg/ml				100 µg/ml					60 µg/ml			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4		1	2	3	4
<i>E. coli</i>	13	12	13	11	12	12	10	11	10	10	9	10	8	9	9	10	7	#	#	7	31
<i>Citrobacter</i>	14	12	11	11	13	11	10	11	11	10	9	11	9	8	8	9	*	*	*	*	28
<i>Vibrio</i>	14	13	12	12	12	13	12	10	10	11	8	9	8	6	6	8	7	#	#	8	29

Control DMSO No Inhibition

*Not measured, # No inhibition, each value is the average of three replicates.

Fig. 4. Graphical representation of antibacterial activity of copper(II) PPC complexes.

age has been investigated by gel electrophoresis using pBR 322 DNA by gel electrophoresis. Control experiment using DNA alone (lane 1) does not show any significant cleavage. The cleavage efficiency of (1-3) (lane 2-7) in the presence and absence of H₂O₂ (Fig. 5). Complex (4) also showed similar behavior (Fig. 6). Observed results

showed that the copper(II) complexes cleave DNA as compared to control DNA but they do not cleave DNA (lane 3, 5 and 7) in the presence of H₂O₂. Probably this may be due to the formation of redox couple of the copper ion. Even in the absent of oxidant, the copper complexes exhibit considerable DNA cleavage activity (lane 2, 4

Fig. 5. Gel electrophoresis showing the chemical nuclease activity of the complexes 1-3 on pBR 322 plasmid DNA, incubation at 37 °C for 1 h in the presence and absence of H₂O₂; Lane 1 - control DNA, Lane 2 - DNA + complex 1, Lane 3 - DNA + complex 1 + H₂O₂, Lane 4 - DNA + complex 2, Lane 5 - DNA + complex 2 + H₂O₂, Lane 6 - DNA + complex 3, Lane 7 - DNA + complex 3 + H₂O₂.

Fig. 6. Gel electrophoresis showing the chemical nuclease activity of the complexes 1-3 on pBR 322 plasmid DNA, incubation at 37 °C for 1 h in the presence and absence of H₂O₂; Lane 1 - control DNA, Lane 2 - DNA + H₂O₂, Lane 3 - DNA + complex 4, Lane 4 - DNA + complex 4 + H₂O₂.

and 6). These observations suggest that the complexes have ability to cleave DNA by non-oxidative mechanism, possibly by hydrolytic path, which remains to be elucidated conclusively. In the presence of trapping agent (DMSO), nuclease activity is diminished. The activity decreases since DMSO acts as a hydroxyl radical scavenger and the exact mechanism remains to be elucidated. The results indicate that the copper(II) complexes plays an important role in the cleavage of DNA. As the complexes were observed to cleave the DNA, it can be concluded that complexes inhibit the growth of the pathogenic organism by cleaving the genome³⁶.

Experimental

Physical measurements :

The elemental analysis for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed on an Elementar Vario ELIII Carlo Erba 1108 Elemental analyzer. UV-Vis spectra were recorded at room temperature on Shimadzu 1601 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded in KBr medium on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. All measurements were carried out at 298 K under a nitrogen atmosphere. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra were recorded with a Varian E-line Century Series EPR spectrometer equipped with a dual cavity and operating at X-band of 100 kHz modulation frequency. Tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) was used as field marker ($g = 2.00277$).

Synthesis of Schiff base (PPC) :

The Schiff base was synthesized by reacting nicotinic acid hydrazide (10 mmol, 1.37 g) and pyrole carboxaldehyde (10 mmol, 0.92 g) in ethanol. *Anal.* Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{10}N_4O$: C, 61.67; H, 4.71; N, 26.15%. Found : C, 61.45; H, 4.45; N, 26.11%. FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 214.22. Found : 215.

Synthesis of $[Cu(PPC)_2](ClO_4)_2$ (1) :

To a methanolic solution (20 mL) of cupric perchlorate hexahydrate (1 mmol, 0.370 g), a solution of PPC (2.0 mmol, 0.428 g) in methanol was added with constant stirring at room temperature. The resultant solution was stirred for 4 h. The solution was filtered and allowed to stand at room temperature for a few days. The light green powder form complex was collected and stored in $CaCl_2$ desiccator. *Anal.* Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{20}Cl_2CuN_8O_{10}$ (1) : C, 38.25; H, 2.92; N, 16.22%. Found : C, 38.65; H, 3.12; N, 15.94%. FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 492.38. Found : 491.99.

Synthesis of $[Cu(PPC)(bipy)](ClO_4)_2$ (2), $[Cu(PPC)(phen)](ClO_4)_2$ (3) and $[Cu(PPC)(PMDT)](ClO_4)_2$ (4) :

Complex 2, 3 and 4 were synthesized following the same procedure as 1, only bipy (1 mmol, 0.156 g) for 2, phen (1 mmol, 0.198 g) for 3 and PMDT (1.0 mmol, 0.173 g) for 4 was added along with 1 mmol PPC. The resultant solution was stirred for 4 h. The solution was filtered and allowed to stand at room temperature for a few days. The complex was collected and stored in $CaCl_2$ desiccator. *Anal.* Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{18}CuCl_2N_6O_9$ (2) : C, 39.86; H, 2.87; N, 13.28%. Found : C, 40.55; H, 2.45;

N, 13.67%. FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 433.95. Found : 435.34; *Anal.* Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{18}CuCl_2N_6O_9$ (3) : C, 42.05; H, 2.76; N, 12.79%. Found : C, 42.45; H, 2.81; N, 12.55%. FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 457.97. Found : 458.32; *Anal.* Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{33}CuCl_2N_7O_9$ (4) : C, 36.96; H, 5.12; N, 15.08%. Found : C, 37.17; H, 5.65; N, 15.95%. FAB Mass (m/z) Calcd. : 451.06. Found : 451.26.

Bioactivity measurements :

The superoxide dismutase activity (SOD) of the present copper(II) complexes were evaluated using alkaline DMSO as source of superoxide radicals (O_2^-) generating system in association with nitrobluetetrazoliumchloride (NBT) as a scavenger of superoxide³⁷. The *in vitro* antibacterial activities were tested against *Escherichia (E.) coli*, *Citrobactor (C.) gillenii* and *Vibro (V.) cholera* and comparison were made with standard antibiotics. The agar disk diffusion method was adopted for determination of antibacterial activity³⁸. Autoclaved Nutrient agar medium was poured in to sterile Petri-dish and allowed to solidify. Petri-dishes were seeded with bacterial species. Paper disc was placed at the dish after dipping test compound (DMSO solution). The width of the growth inhibition zone around the disc was measured after 24 h incubation at 37 °C. DNA cleavage experiments were performed by agarose gel electrophoresis method³⁹. The efficiency of DNA cleavage was measured by determining the ability of the complexes to form open circular (OC) and nicked circular (NC) DNA from its super coiled (SC) form. The DMSO solution ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) containing metal complexes (5 μL , 250 μM) were taken in a clean Eppendroff tube and 1 μg of pBR 322 DNA was added. The content were incubated for 30 min at 30 °C and loaded on 0.8% agarose gel after mixing 3 μL of loading buffer (0.25% bromophenol blue + 0.25% xylene cynaol + 30% glycerol sterilized distilled water). The electrophoresis was performed at constant voltage (75 V) until the bromophenol blue reached upto $\frac{3}{4}$ length of the gel. Further, the gel was stained for 10 min by immersing it in ethidium bromide solution (5 $\mu g/ml$ of water) and then de-stained for 10 min by keeping it in sterile distilled water. The plasmid bands were visualized by photographing the gel under a UV transilluminator. The reactions were carried out under oxidative and/or hydrolytic condition.

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